

Network Research Data Support

Roadmap 2026 – 2030

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What do we want to achieve with the NeRDS roadmap?

The NeRDS roadmap aims to develop a robust and professional ecosystem for research support at VU. This initiative builds on the foundation established over the past years and enhances the strategic goals outlined in the institutional plan and the VU research strategy. The roadmap presents a strategic and integrated approach to the intentional deployment and further development of research data management services. Its primary goal is to ensure the continued relevance and scientific excellence of VU while contributing to the creation of outstanding facilities that facilitate innovative research.

Reading Guide

Introduction

This section provides a brief overview of the current state of research support at VU and the organisation of such efforts. It also examines key frameworks and external factors that are crucial for implementing the roadmap. More detailed information can be found in Appendices 1 and 2.

Ambitions, Themes, and Goals

This section outlines the roadmap's ambitions, detailing the four themes it encompasses. It also describes the long-term goals targeted for 2030 and the associated activities planned for 2026 and 2027.

Appendices 1 and 2

These appendices contain a detailed description of the current status of data and software management at VU, as well as the frameworks and external factors that influence the implementation of the roadmap.

Appendix 3

This appendix specifies the community activities that support the implementation of the roadmap.

Introduction

Why this roadmap?

VU's mission in research is to take responsibility for the future of humanity and the planet through fundamental and applied scientific inquiry. "Our research is high-quality, groundbreaking, and has significant scientific and societal impact."¹ To realise this ambition, priorities and strategic goals have been defined in the VU Research Strategy 2033. Central to this strategy is fostering a broader-minded attitude and strong value orientation among our researchers, articulated through four strategic themes that bring together existing initiatives while launching new ones to drive the desired transformation².

For many years, VU has worked to improve the accessibility, reusability, and integrity of its scientific knowledge, enabling researchers and lecturers to make their research and teaching outputs and processes Open and FAIR. Applying the FAIR principles increases research impact by making data more widely available and facilitating reuse³. At the same time, researchers face growing demands for computing power, data storage, and network capacity. Access to high-quality, low-threshold ICT infrastructure is therefore essential. Researchers also require more targeted support to effectively access and use this infrastructure. Such support is increasingly urgent due to funder requirements for research data and software management, institutional duties of care as outlined in the Dutch Code of Conduct for Scientific Integrity (NGWI), and compliance obligations related to security and privacy.

The NeRDS (Network Research Data Support) Roadmap addresses these challenges from a research support perspective. In line with the VU Research Strategy, its goal is to help create an inspiring campus environment with excellent research support and facilities. Through the activities defined in the 2026–2030 roadmap, we will ensure a solid foundation for high-quality support for researchers at all stages of their work, while making services more efficient, accessible, and user-friendly. This is achieved by organising support as close as possible to researchers and research practice, and by strengthening networks that connect services through an integrated approach.

The support organisation for data and software management operates across several layers. At the central level, the University Library (RDM team) and IT (ITvO) provide support, with approximately 20 FTE allocated to these functions. Faculty-level support is organised in diverse ways. For example, FGB has a large support team comprising data stewards, data managers, and privacy champions, while BETA works with RDM coordinators who focus on awareness and knowledge transfer. The remaining faculties typically operate with smaller teams, where the roles of data steward and privacy champion are often combined in a single position.

¹ VU Onderzoeksstrategie, VU Instellingsplan (In Dutch)

² See VU Onderzoeksstrategie (In Dutch)

³ FAIR principles: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

Frameworks for the roadmap⁴

The NeRDS roadmap defines the roles and activities of the NeRDS network for the coming years and safeguards the continuity of services in data and software management. It is not a static document but evolves in response to ongoing developments. The growth of current services has established a solid foundation, enabling researchers to rely on a well-functioning and professional data management ecosystem. However, rapid technological change makes it essential to define clear directions for further development. Several frameworks guide this process:

1. Alignment with the VU Research Strategy 2023–2033

- The roadmap is aligned with the VU Research Strategy, which centres on four strategic themes. Research support forms the core of the NeRDS roadmap and focuses on strengthening the digital research infrastructure. Transparency, responsible data accessibility, and knowledge security are central to this effort. Achieving these ambitions requires sustained investment in open and flexible infrastructures, data-driven research, and training.

2. Growing demand for RDM services and infrastructure

- Since 2018, substantial investments have been made in a broadly deployable data management ecosystem and the NeRDS network. Usage has increased by approximately 25% annually, reflected both in the number of support requests and in data volumes⁵. Demand for new functionalities, high-performance computing (HPC), and AI capacity is also rising. Continued development is therefore essential to uphold FAIR principles and meet researchers' evolving needs⁶.

3. Developments in digital autonomy and open infrastructures

Broader trends in digital autonomy, data sovereignty, and open infrastructures increasingly shape the roadmap. European initiatives such as the Barcelona Declaration highlight the importance of open research information and reduced dependence on commercial platforms. In parallel, TRUST principles and knowledge security are gaining importance as foundations for sustainable, dependable, and transparent data management solutions.

⁴ A comprehensive description of the current state of research data management at VU University Amsterdam is included in Appendix 1. A comprehensive description of the frameworks and external factors is included in Appendix 2.

⁵ For this, see the RDM Monitor 2024. This clearly shows the growth in demand for support and the use of RDM infrastructure. Not included here is the growth in support from the faculty data stewards. This also increases annually by a comparable percentage.

⁶ In addition, this also requires an upscaling of support capacity. With the existing capacity, we are reaching a limit, and there will come a point when support will be under pressure, unless we can respond appropriately.

The roadmap is further shaped by four critical factors. First, government-imposed budget cuts constrain growth in line with rising demand for support services and infrastructure, necessitating greater efficiency, as expanding staff and resources is not straightforward.

Second, artificial intelligence (AI) plays a dominant role. Its rapid and unpredictable development requires strategic choices. For VU, this means strengthening AI expertise, expanding networks of AI researchers and support staff, and integrating AI into support processes to make them more effective and scalable.

A significant development is the enhancement of national collaboration in data and software management. This progress is facilitated through networks like the Digital Competence Centres (DCCs) and Dutch research software engineers. Furthermore, the establishment of an Integrated Infrastructure for Open Science is serving as a strong catalyst for national cooperation. *The Strategic Plan for an Integrated Infrastructure for Open Science*⁷ aims to establish a reference model for an integrated ecosystem, which will serve as a benchmark for the further development of the VU ecosystem.

Funding opportunities and collaborative initiatives present valuable prospects. Through Open Science NL (NWO) and the network of Digital Competence Centres (DCCs), institutions can combine their expertise, share services, and collectively tackle identified gaps and priorities. This collaborative approach is vital for managing limited resources and effectively responding to technological challenges.

⁷ Projectgroep SPII: [Contouren Open Science Infrastructuur](#), Strategisch plan Integrale Infrastructuur voor Open Science, deel 1 (In Dutch).

STRENGTHS

Talking about
- Tools and data
without thinking
about IT

Integration
in the Dutch
Research landscape

NERDs:
- Provide innovative
solutions
- motivation to
deliver

personal
touch

Not so good
at choosing
and implementing
new solutions
③

good
at supporting
implemented
solutions

Basic infrastructure
is in place

Collaboration
with other parties
(VODA consortium)
is necessary &
increasing

NERDs
network in
place

Silo's in
support:
not only
better, but
RDM - IX

OPPORTUNITIES

③ Database creation
on open source
software and
algorithm solutions

Moving away from
powerful suppliers
because of the
threat of lock-ins

mutual
interest in
making ①
happen

Working on
similar research
support issues
together with
universities

limited
funds

Cooperation
today
Bel

SURF
②+③

NL + Eu
€
Support

②
NWO
support

OSNL calls
↓
form consortia
↓
collaborative
action!

Open source
community

lack of investment
and too high
ambitions

Roadmap: ambitions, themes, and goals

Ambitions

With the 2026–2030 roadmap, we reinforce VU’s strategic ambitions and continue to build on existing infrastructure and support services for data and software management to put Open Science into practice. Transparency and responsible access to research are central to VU’s approach and, by extension, to that of the Research Data Support Network. A robust and professional infrastructure and support framework are essential prerequisites. Together, they must ensure that research data are FAIR and shared openly wherever possible.

Realising this openness requires continued investment in existing services, primarily by ensuring that the fundamentals are in place. This includes providing tools for secure online collaboration, reliable and secure storage solutions, and online environments for documenting research projects. While these facilities already exist, they require continuous improvement and, where possible, transition to open infrastructures. Alongside technical provisions, researchers also need professional training and guidance to work consciously in accordance with FAIR principles. This, too, is an ongoing effort, encompassing discipline-specific training for academic and support staff, as well as students, to support them in adopting Open Science practices.

The 2026–2030 roadmap builds on the strong foundation established in recent years, positioning the Research Data Support Network as a key driver, connector, and catalyst for change. To effectively advance VU’s Open Science objectives and guide NeRDS activities, we have defined four central themes. Each theme shapes a coherent strategy for the targeted deployment and further development of research data management services, all within our available resources. This approach intentionally aligns the roadmap with the VU Institutional Plan, the VU Research Strategy, and the University Library’s multi-year plan.

Themes and goals

The roadmap themes are further elaborated below, with a distinction between two phases

- Short-term implementation (2026–2027). This phase is predictable and can be defined through concrete activities and objectives, some of which are already underway. These are described in more detail below ⁸.

⁸ More detailed and concrete implementations of this are provided in the annual plans of the relevant services, departments, and teams. For example, the 2026 annual plan of the Research Data Support Network will provide a concrete implementation of the activities formulated in the roadmap. The roadmap serves as the strategic and tactical framework for this.

- Long-term planning (2028–2030). This phase is inherently less predictable and therefore cannot yet be translated into specific activities. Instead, it is guided by longer-term strategic ambitions that serve as a directional horizon. These objectives will be further developed and specified in 2027.

Theme	Strategic Ambition
1. Consolidating services and collaboration	Strengthening the chain of research support, consisting of a system of data and software management services.
2. Visible and usable services	Ensuring optimal visibility and usability of the data and software management ecosystem, and further increasing awareness regarding FAIR and Open Science principles.
3. Academic values	Achieving an open and flexible infrastructure based on FAIR, CARE, and TRUST principles, aimed at ensuring digital sovereignty and promoting transparency, fairness, and sustainability.
4. Responsible use of AI in support and research	Exploring the possibilities and risks of using AI in relation to data and software management, as well as the use of AI in research practice.

Because Themes 1 and 2 fall within the core responsibilities of the Research Data Support Network, it takes a leading role in their implementation. For Themes 3 and 4, the Network adopts a more supporting role, as these areas are still evolving rapidly and leadership primarily lies elsewhere, for example, with the AI Competence Network (AICN) in the domain of artificial intelligence.

Together, the four themes and their associated strategic ambitions define the target state for 2030. For each theme, the roadmap outlines what is expected to be achieved by the end of this period.

Theme 1 Consolidate and collaborate	Theme 2 Visible and usable services	Theme 3 Academic values	Theme 4 Responsible AI
<p>VU Amsterdam has a flexible and professional support organisation tailored to the needs of researchers</p> <p>VU Amsterdam's research infrastructure is reliable, flexible, and future-proof</p> <p>This research infrastructure is part of an (inter)national network of services</p>	<p>The research support chain is optimally coordinated, and services collaborate closely</p> <p>VU Amsterdam has a user-friendly platform for handling administrative tasks</p> <p>VU Amsterdam has an up-to-date and easily accessible data management resource</p> <p>VU Amsterdam has a curriculum focused on competency development for support professionals</p>	<p>At least half of the data management services consist of open infrastructure</p> <p>These connect to international infrastructures such as EOSC and OpenAIRE</p> <p>Researchers and support professionals are able to apply the principles of FAIR, CARE, and TRUST</p>	<p>VU Amsterdam has a curriculum for AI competency development for support professionals</p> <p>NeRDS collaborates closely with the AICAN and relevant external partners on this</p> <p>VU Amsterdam has practical AI applications that ensure more efficient handling of repetitive tasks</p>

Theme 1: Consolidate and Collaborate

The **strategic goal** of this theme is to enhance the research support system, which includes data and software management services. We aim to offer professional, efficient, and user-friendly assistance to researchers at all stages of their research, closely aligned with research practices. Our existing foundation consists of a reliable, scalable, and future-proof infrastructure that follows the VU IT approach, which emphasises a cloud-first strategy, autonomy, and governance.

By 2030, VU will have:

- A strong and efficient collaboration between researchers and a professional support organisation, following the principle that support is organised as close as possible to research practice (the foundation is in order).
- A reliable, scalable, and future-proof system of infrastructural data management facilities, used and managed in collaboration with other institutions where possible, and suitable for working with sensitive data.
- A strong and professional collaboration with other (Dutch) institutions in the field of research infrastructure and support.

In 2026 and 2027, we will be working, among other things, on:

1. Research Practice

- Clearly defining the roles and responsibilities of the various staff within the support organisation (both central and decentralised).
- Further developing the annual RDM monitor, in which we include more data regarding the use of support services from the faculty support teams and supplement it with data from the Open Science monitor.
- Developing a reflective monitor in which we measure the impact of the support organisation and, based on that, adjust as needed.
- Conducting a third User Experience survey in which we ask about the use and experience of research support and services. This will also include ITvO services in addition to RDM services.
- Realising integrations between different RDM solutions based on the needs expressed by the research practice⁹.

2. Future-Proof Research Infrastructure¹⁰

- Standardising data management provisions wherever possible based on desired functionalities and common needs.
- Broadening and strengthening the functionality of iRODS/Yoda. We do this in a joint project conducted by the Yoda consortium, funded by OSNL. VU is the overall project leader¹¹.
- Drawing up a policy for the storage of research data.
- Completing the migration to SciStor 2.0.
- Developing (or joining existing initiatives for) solutions for working with sensitive data based on the FAIR principles through specialised tools such as the Research Data Exchange and SANE (Secure Analysis Environment).
- Exploring the possibility of setting up a national facility for long-term preservation of research data. Linked to this is the development of policy, organisation of responsibilities, and determination of financial consequences for long-term archiving of research data, in line with data governance policy.
- Developing and implementing workflows and processes for data deletion when necessary.
- Developing, implementing, and coherently communicating an adapted cost and billing model for the storage of research data.
- Further developing the VU High Performance Compute (HPC) cluster, ADA HPC.
- Embedding SciCloud into the IT maintenance cycle.
- Consolidating data management solutions: where possible, licenses/services with overlapping functionality are combined or responsibly phased out (as previously done with Qualtrics and eLab journals).

⁹ This can include, among other things, linking eLabNext with LabServant and implementing a persistent identifier system for research projects (RAID).

¹⁰ By infrastructure, we mean both the technical facilities and the organisational setup of research support. In this roadmap, the concept of a data management ecosystem is often used for this.

¹¹ Funding for a 4-year project has been granted by OSNL (NWO)

- Creating effective structural solutions for managing student data based on initiatives from the Education Domain. Clearly defining roles and responsibilities is essential.
- Exploring the possibilities for setting up a research software engineering service through a pilot.

3. Collaboration

- Strengthening collaboration with other knowledge institutions through national networks such as the consultation of local and thematic digital competence centres, to make better use of shared knowledge and services.
- Strengthening and professionalising the Yoda consortium.
- Participating in relevant (inter)national collaborations and projects that provide knowledge and experience (including the development of a reference model for open science infrastructure, the strategic plan for integrated infrastructure for open science).
- Strengthening collaboration with SURF. We do this through regular meetings with SURF on services (supplier management), but also by seeking cooperation regarding shared infrastructure and RDM services.
- Further positioning the Research Support Team within IT.
- Exploring possibilities to connect with European infrastructures such as OpenAIRE and EOSC.

Theme 2: Visible and Usable Services

The **goal** of this theme is to provide clear guidance and dedicated support by enhancing the visibility and usability of the data and software management ecosystem. We aim to raise awareness about FAIR and Open Science principles. This will facilitate the publishing, sharing, and reusing of research data more efficiently, contributing to a more open and accessible scientific research landscape. Additionally, we are working to increase awareness of security and privacy issues, as well as data-driven research related to AI applications.

By 2030, VU will have:

- An integrated chain of research support that is organisationally embedded, with roles and responsibilities clearly defined.
- An integrated, user-friendly, and adaptive environment for all administrative actions related to research projects (Research Administration Platform).
- An optimally searchable and usable information source regarding data and software management, collaboratively developed and managed by central services and faculties (Research Support Handbook), guiding researchers to the most appropriate solution.
- A system of training for researchers and support professionals focused on skills development and professionalisation.

In 2026 and 2027, we will work, among other things, on:

1. Chain of Research Support

- Organising, documenting, and coordinating the chain of research support based on existing services, roles, and responsibilities.
- Integrating other services relevant to research support into the NeRDS network, such as IXA-GO and Administrative and Legal Affairs.
- Optimising the findability of support professionals (who-is-who and the roles associated with them).
- Developing a product and service catalogue based on the information researchers need to make optimal use of the right services when required.
- Ensuring better recognition and appreciation of the tasks and responsibilities of support professionals (for example, by establishing a VU Data steward Award).
- Developing and communicating onboarding and offboarding documentation and training for both new researchers and added support professionals.

2. Research Administration Platform

- Developing and implementing the Research Administration Platform in all faculties and for all administrative actions related to data and software management.
- Developing guidelines for research projects in the form of a 'Researcher Journey metro map.'
- Developing a decision tree on what to do with research data after the 10-year retention period has expired.
- Developing an awareness and information campaign regarding the Research Administration Platform.
- Exploring possibilities for integrating processes that currently (still) fall outside the scope of the RAP, such as project control, advising on maintenance grants, systems for booking research equipment, and management of research populations.

3. Findability and usability of services

- Developing user-friendly documentation of the RDM tools recommended and managed by VU. This will be linked to the Research Support Handbook.
- Expanding and improving existing decision support tools: storage finder, data classification assist, and support finder.
- Developing communication tools regarding data and software management services available to VU researchers.
- Improving the findability and accessibility of support professionals at all different levels and topics. Displaying VU data services on the EOSC service catalogue in the EU- and NL- nodes¹².

4. Training and Competence Development

- Developing and providing a system of training for researchers focused, among other things, on data and software management, responsible and safe use of AI, and knowledge security, including discipline-specific training related to interoperability and reuse of research data. We do this wherever possible and relevant in collaboration with the education and operations domains, as there are similar challenges within these domains.
- Developing a system of training for support professionals aimed at further professionalisation and competence development.
- Developing training and information resources aimed at helping researchers make choices about best practices regarding digital sovereignty, such as where to store data in the short and long term, and how to exchange data safely.
- Developing and providing data and software management workshops for postdocs and supervisors.
- Raising awareness of the importance of data and software management and the use and costs of services and infrastructure.

¹² <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/news/eosc-eu-node-resource-catalogue>

- Strengthening existing initiatives around data and software management, such as research support hackathons, the Bytes & Bites community, and data conversations¹³.
- Facilitating and nurturing communities of practice around 'new' themes such as interoperability, open hardware, and faculty-specific interests.
- Setting up HPC literacy training for HPC users.

Theme 3: Academic Values

The **strategic goal** of this theme is to realise an open and flexible infrastructure wherever possible, based on the FAIR, CARE, and TRUST principles, aimed at safeguarding digital sovereignty and promoting transparency, fairness, and sustainability. Digital sovereignty is a necessary condition to secure fundamental academic values, such as individual academic freedom and institutional autonomy, in the digital and geopolitical era. Control over scientific knowledge, publications, data, metadata, and the required infrastructure must, as much as possible, remain with researchers and research institutions and be widely shareable. In doing so, we translate the public values of VU, as described in the institutional plan and VU research strategy, into academic values concerning data and software management practices.

By 2030, VU will have:

- Open infrastructural solutions for data and software management services wherever this is possible and desirable. Data management and storage will be secured in common, usable, dependable, and ethically responsible solutions.
- A connection to a federated network of repositories in which storage and long-term preservation of research results are guaranteed. In addition, we are in line with Dutch and European initiatives for large-scale storage and computing.
- A broad awareness about and application of the FAIR, CARE, and TRUST principles. VU research results are as open and FAIR as possible, supplemented by the CARE principles (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics).

In 2026 and 2027, we will work on:

1. Open Research Infrastructure

- Exploring the possibilities of switching to open source or solutions offered by European suppliers for existing tools within the VU data management infrastructure.
- Conducting a pilot with NextCloud in collaboration with SURF.
- Exploring the possibilities of using the open tools and infrastructures developed and managed by OpenAIRE.
- Improving and strengthening the functionality of Yoda as a universally applicable data management solution for all VU researchers that optimally matches the research practices of different disciplines.
- Exploring the possibilities of broadening the procurement policy about data management solutions in which public values are given a more key role than is currently the case in the purchase and implementation of new systems, especially where commercial solutions are concerned.

2. Federation of data management solutions

- Contributing to and connecting to the integrated infrastructure for open science. This is under development and should provide a reference architecture that defines the different building blocks and elements of an open science infrastructure.
- Exploring the possibilities to connect with the developments towards data spaces. These should enable researchers to share data and collaborate in a way that meets both researchers' needs and regulatory needs¹⁴.
- Increasing the possibilities of interdisciplinary sharing and reuse of research data through the standardisation of metadata and data documentation.

3. Application of FAIR, CARE, and TRUST principles

- Monitoring research results related to FAIR, with particular emphasis on the interoperability and reusability of research results. We will use existing solutions, offered where possible via OpenAIRE and EOSC.
- Joining the movement towards Recognition & Rewards by ensuring that information about research projects is easily available for review by supervisors.
- The application of the TRUST principles to research data stored and managed by VU. These principles complement the FAIR principles by focusing on reliable and sustainable management within data repositories themselves, which is essential for keeping data a

¹⁴ For this, we work together with SURF's public values program.

trustworthy and valuable resource for science and society.

- The drafting of an updated version of the VU data and software management policy and the data classification policy, in which, in addition to FAIR, more attention is given to the CARE and TRUST principles.

Theme 4: Responsible Use of AI in Support and Research

The **strategic goal** of this theme is to examine the opportunities and risks of using AI in data and software management, as well as in research practice. AI applications are increasingly integrated into the core activities and operational processes of institutions. This necessitates developing skills, support systems, and frameworks for the responsible use of AI tools. This theme aligns with the objectives and activities of the VU AI Competence Network (AICN), with a particular focus on using AI for data and software management. As demand for specialised AI skills grows, it becomes increasingly important to learn how to manage them responsibly.

By 2030, VU will have:

- A curriculum aimed at supporting professionals, focusing on providing training in AI competence, in combination with training in knowledge security and privacy.
- Optimal collaboration between the AICN and the RDM Support Desk, supporting researchers with expertise and knowledge about the use and implications of AI.
- A transparent, adequate, safe, and up-to-date infrastructure for AI applications to support and automate research, aimed at reducing manual and repetitive actions and tasks.

In 2026 and 2027, we will work on, among other things:

1. Training

- Developing, in collaboration with the AICN, a training offering for support professionals focused on AI competence. This should ensure that the knowledge within the support organisation is of sufficient quality to advise researchers on the use of AI solutions.
- Organising, in collaboration with peer institutions via the DCC network, training and workshops focused on the application of AI in relation to digital sovereignty, knowledge security, and privacy.

2. Support

- Developing guidelines regarding the use of AI in research practice and integrating AI into data and software management policies.
- Setting up and supporting a VU-wide community of practice focused on sharing knowledge and experiences with the application of AI in relation to data management.

3. Applications

- Exploring the possibilities for applying AI to automate research practices and reduce routine tasks, such as filling out forms that repeatedly request the same information, in collaboration with SURF and other universities. In doing so, we are always looking for time-saving and efficiency-enhancing solutions.
- This exploration will, in any case, be conducted in relation to the development of the Research Administration Platform.
- Another application is reviewing Data Management Plans. Internationally, solutions for this are already being developed, with which we can experiment.
- Further developing the search functionality for the research support handbook based on the Nebula platform.

Appendix 1

Research Data Management at VU

The Research Data Support Network (NeRDS)¹⁵ is a multidisciplinary collaboration that supports researchers in responsible and efficient data management. This network includes services from the University Library, IT, faculty support services, and other departments such as the legal department and the grants office, which work closely together to support researchers. NeRDS is also an active community where researchers and support staff meet, inspire each other, share knowledge and skills, and help one another. By combining our knowledge and strengths, we achieve results that would not be possible for individual teams. The goal is to provide researchers with high-quality support in facilitating good data management and to enable them to work according to the FAIR principles, thereby increasing the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of research results. The network's activities can be divided into four pillars: Infrastructure, Innovation, Information & Support, and Training.

INFRA- STRUCTURE

Provide user support on the technical infrastructure for data- and software management

- Organise the on- and off boarding of users
- Provide (hands-on) support for tools
- Develop and organise workflow- and process management
- Monitor the usage of services

INNOVATION

Improvement of existing service infrastructure & implementation of new tools and functionalities

- Coordination of innovative projects
- Development of new functionalities
- Participate in national- and international developments/projects
- Roadmap development

INFORMATION & SUPPORT

Provide support and advice on data- and software management related questions

- Maintain an RDM Support Desk
- Provide DMP reviews
- Develop and maintain information channels
- Develop and maintain the data- and software management Policy

TRAINING

Develop, provide and host Data- and software management training

- Develop and provide RDM training for PhDs
- Develop and provide RSM training for PhDs
- Facilitate communities of practice

¹⁵ The Network Research Data Support is the implementation by VU of the Digital Competence Centre, in which universities have pooled their offerings of support services.

In recent years, VU has made significant strides in research support and services. The VU Research Data Support program, conducted between 2019 and 2023, delivered a wide range of services, thereby strengthening the RDM infrastructure and support for researchers in the areas of data and software management. These include the establishment of the RDM Support Desk, the appointment of both central data stewards (positioned at the University Library) and faculty data stewards (with a target of 1 FTE per 500 researchers), and the provision of information resources such as the RDM Handbook and the Writing a DMP course. In addition, investment has been made in the technical infrastructure for data management, which has led to the implementation of including iRods/Yoda, Research Drive, the Open Science Framework, and eLabNext. This has professionalised the services provided to researchers. The image below shows the various data and software management services that researchers can use and receive support for. This support ecosystem consists of both infrastructure and support services. The latter represents the human capital, the professional support organisation consisting of (faculty) data stewards, privacy champions, data managers, software engineers, IT support, functional administrators, metadata professionals, RDM coordinators, etc.

VU Data- and Software Management Services 2024

Appendix 2

Frameworks for the Roadmap

There are several reasons for creating this roadmap. Primarily, it seeks to clarify the roles and activities of the NeRDS network in relation to research support. The network is vital for maintaining consistent services in data and software management. This situation is not static; it is subject to continuous change. The progress made in developing existing services has established a solid foundation, allowing researchers to access a well-functioning and professional data management ecosystem.

With rapid technological advancements, including the application of AI, any stagnation in our efforts could result in decline. Therefore, it is crucial to have clear guidelines for the further development of the data management ecosystem. Additionally, the requirements for this ecosystem are constantly evolving, driven not only by technological innovations but also by shifts in research practices. This necessitates ongoing attention and the continual enhancement of services and infrastructure.

A second important reason for improvement is the ongoing growth in the use of VU's data management infrastructure and services. This growth necessitates making these services more efficient and user-friendly. For instance, the number of inquiries received annually by researchers at the RDM Support Desk and faculty data stewards has increased by 25%. Additionally, there is a significant rise in the use of VU-recommended and managed data management solutions. Both the number of users and the actual usage volume of stored data continue to grow each year. This trend applies to all solutions managed by VU, including Yoda, Research Drive, SciStor, DataverseNL, and OSF. The increase is evident not only within the central RDM Support Desk but also at the faculty level, where support from data stewards and privacy champions is also on the rise annually.

A third reason for this need for improvement is the growing initiatives for open research information, as outlined in the Barcelona Declaration¹⁶. These initiatives are crucial because substantial amounts of essential research information, which are vital for resource allocation and evaluating researchers and institutions, are currently locked in closed infrastructures managed by commercial providers. Based on the developments mentioned above, several frameworks and external factors also influence the implementation of the roadmap.

¹⁶ <https://barcelona-declaration.org/>

VU research strategy and the VU institutional plan

The VU research strategy is centred around four strategic themes: (1) talents in teams, (2) dynamic networks, (3) research support, and (4) transparency and reputation. Each of these themes requires a professional and adaptable organisation and infrastructure. However, the primary focus of the roadmap is the third theme, research support, specifically concerning the digital research infrastructure. VU's key priorities related to data management and Open Science include ensuring transparency and making research responsibly accessible. This will be supported by robust and open infrastructures. To achieve this, we need to invest in flexible and open infrastructures, promote data-driven research, and develop training and support for data management and knowledge security.

See: [VU Research Strategy 2023-2033](#) (In English)

The growth of technological capabilities and the use of RDM services and support

Since 2018, VU has made significant efforts and investments to enhance research support and the necessary services. This has resulted in a robust data management infrastructure that is accessible to all faculties, disciplines, and researchers. Additionally, the Research Data Support Network has been established to consolidate support activities. By providing broad, easily accessible, and user-friendly services, we have seen an increase in usage. This trend accelerated in 2021, with notable growth in several areas: more inquiries to the support organisation, increased utilisation of infrastructure (including more data and larger volumes being stored and archived), and a rising demand for new functionalities. Furthermore, there is a growing need for computing and GPU capacity, driven in part by the increased use of HPC services and AI.

See [RDM Monitor 2023](#) (In English)

Services related to data management are guided by research practices and the specific needs that arise from them. Our current infrastructure and support systems have been established accordingly. Recognising that this is an evolving situation, we continuously monitor developments and adapt our offerings based on researchers' experiences. We achieve this through annual discussions with all faculties and by conducting a User Experience Survey. This survey evaluates how researchers perceive the support and services related to Research Data Management (RDM) and how they utilise them.

The first survey was conducted in 2020, establishing a baseline for measurement. The second User Experience Survey took place in 2023. The results indicate considerable progress in the

visibility and usability of our services; however, there is still considerable room for improvement. Recommendations for enhancements have been compiled in a report, which will inform our future roadmap.

See: [User Experience Report 2023](#) (In English)

In addition, we are seeing an increase in the application of the FAIR principles. These are the guidelines to make datasets Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR). The trend is to apply these principles to all research outputs, including software and computational workflows, which improves reproducibility and reusability through FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs) and Knowledge Graphs. Due to the explosive growth of data volumes, AI-based automation is being employed to reduce manual tasks, such as data orchestration and quality control. This leads to more content- and data-quality-conscious solutions for data management.

See: [IFLA Trend Report 2024](#) (In English and Spanish) and [SURF Tech Trends Report 2026](#) (In English and Dutch)

Trends and developments regarding digital autonomy, data sovereignty, and open infrastructures.

The main trend in the field of data management, knowledge security, and data sovereignty includes the shift towards open, reliable infrastructures and an increasing emphasis on independent control over data. The Barcelona Declaration aims to transform research by ensuring that research information is openly accessible through academic infrastructures.

See: [Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information](#)

The current geopolitical situation is a significant factor driving the development of digital and data sovereignty. Europe is advocating for digital sovereignty to decrease dependence on American cloud providers and to gain greater control over sensitive data. This initiative includes transferring data from American servers to Europe and investing in European cloud infrastructure.

The exchangeability of research data is threatened by recent political developments in the United States, where restrictions on data exchange have been imposed, and key databases have been taken offline. Additionally, increasing measures for knowledge security are limiting the exchangeability and reusability of data, which jeopardises the principles of open science. The principles of open scientific exchange, academic freedom, and institutional autonomy must remain foundational.

Furthermore, the growing importance of the TRUST principles (Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability, Technology) should be highlighted. These principles are becoming increasingly relevant for data repositories as they complement the FAIR principles by emphasising the management and long-term sustainability of the infrastructure that manages data.

See: [IFLA Trend Report 2024](#), [SURF Tech Trends-rapport 2026](#) and the [KNAW report Academic Freedom in the Netherlands](#) (In Dutch with English Summary)

Several important external factors have a significant impact on the implementation of the roadmap:

Budget cuts: These mean that the capacity needed to match the growth in the use of support services cannot automatically grow as well. This means we need to focus on increasing efficiency because, with the current number of support professionals, we often cannot keep up with the growth. An increase in the number of requests does not automatically mean that we can expand the support organisation accordingly. The same applies to the technical infrastructure. This will have long-term implications and may affect the reputation of support services. Limited capacity and financial resources also mean that large innovation projects cannot be conducted or will have a longer lead time.

AI: The dominant theme is the rapid development and use of AI with a high degree of unpredictability. This transformation is a fact, not a goal, trend, or ambition. The challenge is to translate this into what it means for VU, and particularly for researchers and research support. This requires increasing AI knowledge, strengthening the campus-wide network of AI researchers and supporters, and applying AI internally to improve support.

Collaboration: There is a strengthening of national cooperation in the field of data and software management, including through the network of DCCs and that of the Dutch software engineers. But the development of an integrated Infrastructure for Open Science also provides a strong boost to national collaboration. The *Strategic Plan for Integrated Infrastructure for Open Science*¹⁷ aims to develop a reference model for an integrated ecosystem. This reference model will serve as a benchmark for further development of the VU ecosystem.

Opportunities for external funding and Collaboration: Through the OSNL (NWO), there are various funding options that we should maximise, and we are already pursuing this. Additionally, we should seek to collaborate more effectively with other institutions to avoid duplicating efforts. It is important to explore ways to better leverage each other's services.

¹⁷ Projectgroep SPII: [Contouren Open Science Infrastructuur](#), Strategisch plan Integrale Infrastructuur voor Open Science, deel 1 (In Dutch).

This collaboration can be facilitated by the network of Digital Competence Centres (DCCs), which is a national partnership of local and thematic DCCs¹⁸. As the DCCs are still in development, there is significant potential for cooperation regarding infrastructural services, community management, and coordination/alignment. This collaboration includes learning from one another, sharing expertise, addressing gaps, setting priorities, and developing roadmaps together.

¹⁸ The LDCCs were established to strengthen and coordinate research support, specifically focusing on the management of research data, research software, and research IT/infrastructure. The individual LDCCs primarily focus on enhancing support within their own organisation and are tailored to the needs of their organisation. As a result, they differ in scope, focus, maturity, and structure. The TDCCs (Life Sciences & Health, Natural & Engineering Sciences, and Social Sciences & Humanities) were established to facilitate the strengthening and implementation of domain-specific standards and best practices through project funding and community building. The TDCCs do this in collaboration with the LDCCs and are well represented in DCC-IN. Each individual LDCC, however, includes a range of services (e.g., information provision, advice and consultancy, training, portfolio management, services and tools), community management (e.g., awareness, knowledge exchange), and coordination/alignment (e.g., of organisation-wide services and policies). The TDCCs (Life Sciences & Health, Natural & Engineering Sciences, and Social Sciences & Humanities) were established to facilitate the strengthening and implementation of domain-specific standards and best practices through project funding and community building. The TDCCs do this in collaboration with the LDCCs and are well represented in DCC-IN.in DCC-IN.

Appendix 3

VU data management communities

Introduction

The NeRDS Community comprises enthusiastic employees from Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam. Over the past six years, it has become an important connector among faculties, departments, and services, providing a variety of activities and networking opportunities. The community has grown in response to the increasing demand for Research Data Management (RDM) support within the university. As NeRDS, as a Digital Competence Centre (DCC), continues to evolve accordingly, the NeRDS Community is also entering a new phase of development.

This document briefly outlines the course set for the NeRDS community based on the themes of the NeRDS roadmap 2026-2029, supported by examples of events and initiatives for 2026. This document discusses the NeRDS User Research Report 2023, the VU Research Strategy for 2023-2033, and the fundamentals of scientific community engagement by CSCCE.

From growth to autonomy

As noted, substantial growth over the past six years has established a strong foundation on which we now operate.

Cherish what works

This new course establishes a clear goal while building on existing elements that contribute to success. The RDS newsletter, Open Science Connect, as well as Data Conversations, Data Steward Meet-ups, and RDS Meet-ups will continue in their current format and name. However, many of these familiar components will gradually become more structured. For example, Data Conversations will evolve from a fixed format; under the new title of Data Conversation, they will include workshops, panel discussions, and various interactive formats beyond lunch hours. This change encourages participants to take greater ownership of their data discussions, supported by the knowledge, networks, and resources of the NeRDS Community.

Channelling Growth

As part of the new strategy, we are focusing on strong onboarding to facilitate and enhance the engagement of community members. Over recent years, the central university library has emerged

as the focal point for the community. While this central role aids communication and provides a gateway into the network, it also creates vulnerabilities in engagement. The central library cannot maintain all connections, making it challenging for network members who rely on one or two key contacts to stay connected with the community. The new strategy aims to guide new network members toward like-minded individuals within their own department, faculty, or service. By doing so, we hope to support their engagement in a decentralised manner and foster the development of communities of practice.

From growth to autonomy

A community is dynamic; it grows, develops, and evolves according to organic principles. The NeRDS community has experienced significant growth over the past few years through a communicative relationship. In essence, the community manager shares information with the broader network, which then engages with this input, similar to the way a newsletter or lecture functions.

Over time, an additional component has emerged: community members now actively request information or contribute their own insights to be shared within the network. Collaborative events like the Summer and Winter Training Days and the Data Steward Meet-up further emphasise this collaboration. However, the role of the community manager remains vital in fostering these interactions.

This ambition aims to actively encourage co-creation within the NeRDS Community. It is important to note that not all communities need to adopt a co-creation model; the participation models mentioned earlier cater to different types of communities, and none is inherently superior to another. However, the NeRDS Community has now reached a scale and level of diversity where co-creation is both practical and beneficial.

At this stage, it is natural that some participants begin to branch off as activities and information no longer fully align with their specific interests or needs. Rather than losing these participants, NeRDS aims to support them in pursuing their interests more autonomously. In practice, this means groups may split off to form new communities that function as satellites around the larger core community. Through co-creation, the core community nurtures these communities of practice, enabling them collectively to achieve more than the sum of their parts.

This approach relieves the core community from the necessity of organising events for every specialisation, niche interest, or temporary issue. At the same time, communities of practice benefit from the support, capacity, and resources provided by the core community. With this guidance, they can concentrate on their specific interests while receiving coaching from the core.

Communities of practice are not projects with predefined end goals, although they may work towards specific outcomes. They dissolve when they are no longer needed, either fading out naturally or, in more favourable cases, reintegrating into the core community. In some instances, a community of practice may continue to exist independently as its own autonomous core community. This dynamic is essential to the health of networks like NeRDS, as it maintains engagement and creates space for new developments and emerging interests.

Growing communities of practice in practice

Within and around NeRDS, several smaller communities already show potential to develop more autonomous forms. Examples include the coders' group VUltures, the Open Hardware community, the Interoperability community, and initiatives such as Bridging Disciplines. The ambition for 2026 is to provide these communities of practice with the resources they need to develop independently.

This initiative will be supported through CSCCE's scaffolding approach, known as community scaffolding. Communities are encouraged to express their wishes, ambitions, and goals, after which tailored support is developed in collaboration with the community manager. This support may include coaching on topics such as navigating VU channels, identifying funding opportunities, and accessing services. Additionally, practical tools like checklists, mailing lists, shared spaces, and financial assistance for basic expenses may be provided.

To actively promote the formation of communities of practice, NeRDS will clearly communicate that such initiatives are explicitly supported. To build on this, a workshop will be organised to explore tools, funding opportunities, and frameworks for establishing a community of practice. In this way, the NeRDS Community offers a platform for groups of interested participants to evolve into fully developed communities of practice.

Members of the community

For events organised directly by the NeRDS Community, the following target groups are distinguished. Under each theme, an indicative mapping shows which initiatives are aimed at which audiences.

Target group	Example roles	What they want	Frequency
Early career researchers	PhDs (Research) Master students	Access to help and guidance within the academic world	Medium (5× per year)
Core research support professional	UB Data Stewards Faculty Data Stewards Privacy Champions	Support, guidance, and access to well-organised research support	High (12× per year)
Open Science Enthusiast	Open Access advocate Open Hardware community Open Software community OSCA Center for Research Integrity and Open Science	Inspiration, recognition, and appreciation	Medium (5× per year)
Research Support Professional	Library professionals Research IT team Faculty Policy professionals	To be part of well-organised research support	Low (3× per year)

Strengthening the roadmap goals through the community

Below, the role of the community in relation to the themes is outlined. In the next version of this appendix, this will be further expanded with concrete community activities.

Theme 1: Consolidating services and collaboration

Goal

Consolidate services and collaboration by achieving a data and software management ecosystem built on complementary services, tools, and infrastructure. The aim is to minimise overlapping functionality while ensuring efficient organisation and optimal usability.

Role of the NeRDS Community

Researchers and support staff should be able to enter NeRDS at any point and be guided to the appropriate services that can assist them further. The NeRDS Community provides the foundation for establishing both professional and personal connections that help participants understand and navigate the network. Faculty-based and specialised services maintain clear channels for evaluating new ideas and developments, helping to prevent duplication while encouraging initiative across the university.

Intended Results

- **RDS Community mailing list:** A direct communication channel for updates within NeRDS to all registered members, sharing not only technical and internal news but also existing information resources.
- **Data Steward Meet-up:** A monthly meeting of central and faculty data stewards. Sessions are organised by the community manager and thematically prepared by one of the data stewards.
- **NeRDS Community Meet-up:** A network-wide thematic update, held quarterly in principle and focused on concrete results.
- **Promotion of departmental collaboration:** Support for interdepartmental meetings and sessions, including room and catering expenses. A playbook will be created to inspire topics and methods that enhance the ecosystem.
- **Summer/Winter training days:** Internal training and professional development for the NeRDS Community.
- **RDM Tooling Day:** An annual introduction to RDM infrastructure, organised in collaboration with technical administrators and ITvO.

Instruments

Early career researchers	RDM Tooling day
Core research support professional	Data Steward Meet-up Summer/Winter training days promotion of department collaboration RDS Community mailing list
Open Science Enthusiast	
Research Support Professional	Promotion of department collaboration RDS Community mailing list RDM Tooling day

Theme 2: Visible and usable services

Goal

Ensure optimal visibility and usability of the data and software management ecosystem, while further increasing awareness of FAIR and Open Science principles.

Role of the NeRDS Community

As the public face of NeRDS, the NeRDS Community communicates successes and developments across Vrije Universiteit in their broadest sense. Through written communication and events, NeRDS is presented as a single, cohesive entity with multiple points of contact and entry. The Community actively keeps the threshold for information and specialist support low, for both researchers and NeRDS-affiliated research support staff.

Results

- **Research Connect:** A bi-monthly update featuring news from the RDS and Open Science community at Vrije Universiteit. It offers an accessible way to gradually explore all aspects of the NeRDS Community.
- **RDM Handbook (sprints):** A central resource for all information on RDM and Open Science, maintained in a shared Git environment. Alongside continuous internal updates, the handbook is refreshed each semester during dedicated day-long sprint sessions.

Instruments

Early career researchers	Research Support Handbook
Core research support professional	Research Connect
Open Science Enthusiast	Research Connect
Research Support Professional	Research Connect Research Support Handbook

Theme 3: Academic Values

Goal

Translate VU's public values into concrete objectives and outcomes for data and software management and research support.

Role of the NeRDS Community

NeRDS stands for Open Science, research integrity, and "good science." In collaboration with partners that promote research integrity and Open Science, the NeRDS Community ensures that all interactions and communications raise awareness of these themes.

This role is twofold. First, NeRDS provides a platform where initiatives from researchers and research support staff are recognised and valued, particularly where such recognition has not yet become standard practice at Vrije Universiteit. The Community actively facilitates celebrating every step toward realising VU's public values. Second, NeRDS serves as the foundation from which concrete goals and outcomes gain momentum and can be effectively achieved.

Results

- **OSCA Open Science Awards:** An annual celebration of Open Science in Amsterdam. In collaboration with OSCA, awards are presented in ten categories to promote and recognise Open Science practices.
- **Open Science Day:** An annual event celebrating all aspects of Open Science, featuring poster presentations and lectures.
- **Data Conversations presents:** Several times per semester, engaged members of the NeRDS Community address cross-faculty topics. With support from the University Library, these sessions can be organised at the faculty or university level, with the format determined by the organising party.
- **Open Science Community Fund:** Supports community-driven Open Science initiatives.
- **Love Data / Data Horror Week:** Activities organised in February and November around the international Love Data and Data Horror Week, in collaboration with the Open Science collective GHOST (Games of Horror for Open Science Training).

Instruments

Early career researchers	Open Science Community fund Data Conversations presents Love Data / Data Horror Week
Core research support professional	Open Science Day Data Conversations presents
Open Science Enthusiast	OSCA Open Science Awards Open Science Day Data Conversations presents Open Science Community fund Love Data / Data Horror Week
Research Support Professional	Open Science Day Data Conversations presents Love Data / Data Horror Week

Theme 4: Use of AI in Support and Research

Goal

Explore the opportunities and risks associated with the use of AI in data and software management, as well as in research practice, including AI literacy. This work aligns with the activities of the VU AI Competence Network.

Role of the NeRDS Community

The NeRDS Community is part of the AI Competence Network and supports its objectives by contributing to community building, in line with the needs identified by the AI network.

Results

- **Bytes and Bites:** A regular meeting of the coding community at Vrije Universiteit, supported by an internal community known as VULTURES, under the supervision of the Research Software Engineer at the University Library.
- **AI Competency Network Community Building**

Instruments

Early career researchers	Bytes and Bites
Core research support professional	
Open Science Enthusiast	
Research Support Professional	Bytes and Bites AI Competence Network Community Building